

How does ICT affect school efficiency in Europe?

Evidence from OECD PISA 2022

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Abstract. This paper investigates how Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) affect school efficiency, drawing on data from the OECD PISA 2022 survey for 5,360 schools across 21 EU countries. While prior literature has examined the relationship between ICT and student performance, limited attention has been given to its impact on school efficiency, defined as the capacity to transform inputs (resources) into educational outcomes (test scores). To address this gap, we adopt a combined methodological approach. First, we estimate school-level efficiency scores using a robust nonparametric order-m model under a meta-frontier framework, distinguishing between local (within-country) and global (cross-country) benchmarks. Our results show a higher average local efficiency (0.87) compared to global efficiency (0.69), with significant variation across countries. We also run a robust conditional efficiency model in which exogenous variables are indicators of ICT availability and use, showing how ICT affects the production model increasing the average efficiency up to 0.85. Furthermore, to enrich the descriptive analysis on the role of ICT, we employ a multilevel random forest model to explore which ICT-related variables best explain efficiency scores. Findings highlight that cognitively engaging digital activities such as student-led research, data analysis, and the use of digital learning games are positively associated with efficiency, especially when used in moderation (i.e., avoiding its excessive use). ICT availability, while necessary, plays a lesser role. These results suggest that the pedagogically-driven integration of ICT, rather than its mere presence, is key to enhancing school efficiency.

Keywords. Schools' efficiency; ICT; OECD PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment)

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1. Introduction

The integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) into educational systems has long been a focus of both academic inquiry and policy intervention. ICT is often heralded as a potential driver of innovation and improvement in education, particularly due to its capacity to enhance learning environments, enable individualized instruction, and improve administrative efficiency. Within this broader discourse, a growing body of empirical research has investigated the role of ICT in shaping the educational production function – that is, the relationship between educational inputs (such as school resources, teaching strategies, and student background) and outputs (typically measured by student achievement) (De Witte & Rogge, 2014). A growing body of research in the field of education economics investigates the role of ICT in shaping the educational production function (Akabayashi et al., 2025), with particular attention to two distinct yet interrelated dimensions: ICT access and availability, referring to the presence and quality of digital infrastructure and equipment; and ICT use for educational activities, which captures the extent and nature of technology integration into instructional practices (Gerick et al., 2017; Comi et al., 2017; Dong & Kula, 2023; Mergoni et al., 2023). The attention that scholars have devoted to this field of research is grounded into both theoretical importance and policy relevance. The debate about the educational policies for promoting a conscious (and effective) use of technology in the educational setting is particularly relevant in Europe. On one side, the European Commission launched the Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027), which contains a strategic vision (and 14 practical actions) to foster the use of ICT in schools towards an inclusive digital learning for all (European Commission, 2020). The necessity of understanding the best use of technology in the educational domain has also been highlighted by the EU Commission's expert group on quality investment in education and training in its final Report (European Commission, 2022; chapter 3.2). The awareness of a clever use of technology has been even more gained after COVID pandemic, when the evidence demonstrates that ICT can make a difference in contrasting learning losses (Bertoletti et al., 2023). The acquisition and development of adequate digital skills have been promoted in Europe not only in general terms for citizens, but also specifically for individuals involved in educational processes (teachers and students) by means of a reference framework, denominated DigCompEdu, which comprises 22 competences organized around 6 areas (European Commission, 2017). Lastly, the recent advent and use of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) calls for an updated understanding of what we know on the role of technology in educational processes, as UNESCO indicates in its recent policy documents and guidelines (UNESCO, 2021; 2023; 2024a; 2024b). Although assessing the impact of GenAI on educational results – on a large scale – is still premature, insights about the potential impact of ICT on schools' activities and results in the past years seems a prerequisite for developing such assessments.

Much of the early academic literature concentrated on the relationship between ICT availability and student performance, often yielding inconclusive or contradictory findings. While some studies suggest that ICT infrastructure can foster improved learning outcomes, others report limited or even negative associations (Fernández-Gutiérrez et al. 2020; Odell et al., 2020a; Vargas-Montoya et al. 2024). A recent literature review by Odell et al. (2020b) synthesizes this debate, highlighting that

while intensive and unfocused ICT use appears counterproductive, a moderate and pedagogically aligned use of digital tools can be positively related to student achievement. While it is clear that a generic use of computers and technology is not conducive to better academic performance (Checchi et al., 2019; Hall & Lundin, 2024), consensus remains elusive, and studies often vary widely in terms of methodology, context, and definitions of ICT-related constructs.

More recently, attention has turned toward a broader conceptualization of school effectiveness, which evaluates how well schools convert a given set of inputs into outputs, rather than focusing solely on performance outcomes, named school efficiency. This efficiency-based perspective allows for a more nuanced understanding of how ICT may contribute to value creation within education systems. However, the literature on the relationship between ICT and school-level efficiency is still relatively limited. Only a few contributions, such as Mergoni et al. (2023) and Agasisti et al. (2023) have explicitly explored this topic using international large-scale assessments like OECD PISA. These studies employed Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) to assess technical efficiency and found diverging results: while ICT use appeared more relevant than availability in EU countries (Mergoni et al.), the reverse held true for Latin American countries (Agasisti et al.). This inconsistency can be attributed to the different stage of development of the countries considered: while in developing countries availability is key, the value added in the developed countries comes with ICT use.

This paper contributes to this emerging strand of research by filling two key gaps in the literature. First, it offers updated empirical evidence based on the most recent OECD PISA 2022 dataset, with a focus on 21 EU countries, thereby providing a timely and policy-relevant analysis. The previous contributions similar to ours deal with PISA 2018 data. Second, it adopts multiple methodological approaches that combine robust order-m and conditional efficiency models with machine learning techniques to explore the relative importance of different ICT-related variables. While the inclusion of ICT variables in the conditional model allows to properly account for the influence of ICT in influencing the school productivity set, the use of machine learning offers a unique opportunity to descriptively visualize the relationship between ICT and efficiency (Shiltz et al., 2018). To our knowledge, this is the first paper that employs this innovative methodology for investigating this specific topic. In doing so, the paper not only advances methodological innovation but also deepens our understanding of which aspects of ICT usage matter most for school efficiency, and under what conditions.

To address these aims, the study is guided by two core research questions: RQ1: What is the level of school efficiency across EU countries, and how do these scores vary by country? RQ2: How are measures of ICT availability and use influence and are associated with school efficiency?

To anticipate the main results, we find that school efficiency increases when ICT variables are included in the model, and that the use of ICT influences school efficiency much more than its availability. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the methodology, while Section 3 presents the data. Section 4 presents the empirical results, first reporting efficiency scores and then identifying the ICT variables mostly associated with efficiency. Finally, Section 5 outlines the main contributions and implications of the study and concludes.

2. Methodology

For the efficiency analysis, all relevant variables - both inputs and outputs - are aggregated at the school level, thereby treating the school as the Decision-Making Unit (DMU) and with a total amount of 5360 schools included. This approach allows for a consistent evaluation of how each school transforms a given set of inputs (e.g., students' socioeconomic background, schools' educational resources) into outputs (e.g., average student performance), while also enabling the assessment of the role played by school-level ICT conditions and practices in explaining variation in efficiency scores. As a first methodological approach, school efficiency is estimated using Constant Return to Scale (CRS), output-oriented efficiency model. In deterministic DEA, the production technology is typically defined as the smallest convex set that includes all observed units. Using the CRS assumption introduced by Charnes et al. (1978), we adopt an output-oriented perspective, where efficiency reflects the potential to proportionally expand outputs without violating feasibility. Thus, using a vector of x inputs and y outputs, efficiency can be expressed as the scalar ϕ :

$$\phi = \sup \{ \phi \mid (x_0, \phi y_0) \in \Psi_{DEA} \} \quad (1)$$

$$\Psi_{DEA} = \{ (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}_+^{p+q} \mid y \leq \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i Y_i ; x \geq \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i X_i ; \text{ and } \gamma_i \geq 0 \forall i \} \quad (2)$$

Where $\phi \geq 1$, and $\phi = 1$ is for efficient DMUs. To align with common practice in DEA, we express the model in a way that maintains the interpretation of output maximization, while also offering a clearer and more intuitive efficiency score. Thus, we report efficiency scores as $1/\phi$. Under CRS, this representation remains consistent with the input-oriented formulation. More in detail, we adopt the robust order- m model introduced by Cazals et al. (2002) and further developed by Daraio and Simar (2007). This nonparametric frontier approach extends traditional Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) by incorporating stochastic robustness. Specifically, the order- m model evaluates the performance of each Decision-Making Unit (DMU) – in this case, the school – against a frontier constructed from the best-performing peers, but only using a subset of m randomly drawn observations rather than the full sample. This technique mitigates the influence of extreme values and outliers, producing more robust and reliable efficiency scores, particularly in the presence of noise and sampling variation. In this case, the production possibility set for an output level y' can be expressed as:

$$\Psi^m(x, y') = (x, y') \in \mathbb{R}_+^{p+q} \mid y \leq \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_i y_i'; x \geq \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_i X_i; \quad (3)$$

and $\gamma_i \geq 0$ for $i = 1 \dots m$

It should be noted that since only $m < n$ units are used to estimate the production possibility set, it is possible to obtain values of the order- efficiency higher than 1. The scores are computed by means of a bootstrap procedure, thus the final order- m score of a unit i over the B replicates is:

$$\theta_i^m = (1 / B) \sum_{b=1}^B \theta_i^{b,m} \quad (4)$$

To capture both within- and cross-country heterogeneity, we apply the model under a meta-frontier framework, distinguishing between two types of efficiency. (i) Global Efficiency is calculated by benchmarking each school against the frontier constructed from the entire pooled sample of EU schools. This score enables cross-country comparison and identifies how schools perform relative to the best performers across the 21 countries considered, assuming a common production frontier. (ii) Local Efficiency is calculated by benchmarking each school against the frontier composed of schools within the same country g . This score reflects how efficiently a school performs relative to its national peers, accounting for country-specific constraints and institutional environments.

To account for the influence of ICT on the production possibility set of schools, we also run a conditional order- m DEA model, in which the z exogenous variables are indexes of ICT availability and use. The main difference between unconditional robust and conditional robust approaches is that, in the conditional case, the units to be included in the reference set for the evaluation of unit i are not selected randomly, but accordingly with their similarity with the unit evaluated:

$$\Psi^m(x, y | z) = \{ (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}_+^{p+q} \mid y \leq \sum_{i \in \Gamma^{m,z}} \gamma_i y_i \ ; \ x \geq \sum_{i \in \Gamma^{m,z}} \gamma_i X_i \ ; \ \gamma_i \geq 0 \ ; \ \text{for } i \in \Gamma^{m,z} \} \quad (5)$$

Where $\Gamma^{m,z}$ is the reference set for the unit i . Similarly to the order- m model, the conditional efficiency scores can be computed as the results of a bootstrap procedure, resulting in:

$$\theta_i^{m,z} = (1 / B) \sum_{b=1}^B \theta_i^{b,m,z} \quad (6)$$

To even deeply understand the influence of different measures of availability and use of ICT and following the measure developed by Mergoni et al. (2025), we compute the following measure:

$$R(z) = (1/n) \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{\theta_i^m}{\theta_i^{m,z}} - 1 \right| \quad (7)$$

where z represents the set of contextual variables used in the conditional efficiency estimation, namely the measures of ICT availability and use. In the univariate case, $R(z)$ captures the influence of a single variable on the production process, while in the multivariate case, it reflects interaction effects among the ICT measures. To account for the influence of ICT on efficiency, we computed four composite indicators that are included as z variables and described below in detail. By including the ICT indexes two by two, we can test what combination of ICT availability and use influences efficiency the most. However informative this analysis, it cannot fully exploit full granularity of the data at item level that the PISA allows, given that each question is composed by several single items. To fully explore the richness of the data, we complemented the efficiency model with a descriptive analysis of the association between efficiency scores (as dependent variable) and all the single items related with ICT availability and use. In detail, we employed a multilevel random forest approach, a machine learning technique particularly well suited for handling complex, nonlinear relationships in

hierarchical datasets. In particular, we consider schools nested within countries, thus recalling the meta-frontier approach used before (and, coherently, local efficiency scores are used as dependent variables). By modelling these nested structures explicitly, the multilevel random forest approach allows us to account for both within-country and between-country sources of variability in school efficiency scores. For each school i within country g we estimated the following:

$$y_{ig} = f(\mathbf{x}_{ig}) + b_g + \varepsilon_{ig} \quad (8)$$

Where \mathbf{x}_{ig} is the vector of ICT items, $b_g \sim N(0, \theta^2)$ is the random intercept at country g level, and $\varepsilon_{ig} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ is the error term.

3. Data

This study draws on OECD PISA 2022 wave, focusing on a sample of schools from 21 European Union (EU) countries. The dataset includes both student-level performance indicators and a rich set of school-level contextual variables related to ICT infrastructure and usage. Those variables are obtained as self-reported measures by students and school principals – for technical and further details about the PISA design, see OECD (2023). To capture the input side of the educational production process, three key dimensions are considered. First, the average socioeconomic background of students (ESCS) is used as a proxy for the broader social capital available within the school community. Second, the richness of educational resources (EDURICH) provides an indication of the quality and availability of learning materials and infrastructure that support instruction, and is computed as the reverse of EDUSHORT, an index directly computed by OECD and referred to the shortage of educational materials. Third, the teacher-student ratio (TSRATIO) reflects the human capital intensity of the school, often associated with class size and instructional attention. On the output side, student achievement is measured through the school-level average scores in the three core PISA domains: mathematics, reading, and science. These indicators serve as proxies for the cognitive competencies that schools aim to develop through their educational processes. For each subject the first plausible value is taken and mediated at school level (Aparicio et al., 2022). By using this input-output configuration, the model assesses the relative efficiency of schools in converting educational inputs into student performance. Table 1 reports the descriptive statistics on those variables per country. The number of schools per country ranges from 150 (Ireland) to 810 (Spain), with most countries contributing between 200 and 300 schools. The index of the socio-economic status (ESCS) is built to have a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1 on the overall PISA sample. Among the countries considered there are average positive values in countries like Sweden (0.341) and Ireland (0.315), and lower values in Romania (−0.541) and Bulgaria (−0.363). Educational resources (EDURICH) tend to be higher in Nordic countries, with Denmark (4.229) and Sweden (4.167) at the top, while Greece shows the lowest value (2.899). Student–teacher ratios (TSRATIO) vary moderately, ranging from 0.077 (Germany, Romania) to 0.177 (Slovenia). Performance scores are highest in Estonia (over 500 across all domains) and lowest in Bulgaria and Romania, with particularly low reading scores.

[Table 1] around here

After running the initial efficiency analysis, the model is designed to identify which ICT-related variables are influencing more the school-level efficiency. All ICT variables are collected from the ICT questionnaire (student level) and aggregated at the school level, in line with the conceptualization of the school as the Decision-Making Unit (DMU). Specifically, the analysis considers both structural and behavioural dimensions of ICT in education. On the one hand, the model incorporates measures of ICT availability, quality and accessibility, such as the presence of digital devices (e.g., laptops), the quality of internet connections, and the self-reported digital competencies of teaching staff. These variables, drawn from item IC172 in the PISA dataset, are scored on a four-point Likert scale and reflect the technological readiness of schools and measured through 9 items, as detailed in Table 2.

On the other hand, the model captures different aspects of ICT use in pedagogical practices, distinguishing between general frequency of digital tool usage in daily school life and more specialized, instructional applications. For instance, general ICT usage includes the frequency with which students use laptops or educational software during lessons, based on item IC170, scored on a five-point scale and 7 items. Additionally, the model takes into account how frequently ICT is used in specific subject areas, in particular those tested by PISA, namely mathematics, reading and science, plus computer science classes, as reported in question IC173 that is made of 4 items. Finally, the model integrates measures of ICT use for complex learning activities, such as searching for information online, conducting data analysis, or collaborating on project-based tasks, as captured by item IC174 through 10 items. These indicators aim to reflect the depth and cognitive engagement associated with ICT use, going beyond superficial exposure to digital tools.

Given that the conditional efficiency model could not handle such a big number of items, we created 4 indexes as the mean value per school of all the items that refer to the four questions, as reported in the first column of Table 2 and described with the mean value by country in Table 3. The Access index (access_172) reflects the availability and quality of digital infrastructure in schools, based on items from question set IC172. The Usage index (use_170) summarizes how frequently schools use different types of digital devices and platforms, as reported in IC170. The Pedagogical Intensity index (intensity_173) is based on how often digital tools are used in various subject lessons (IC173), while the Activity index (activities_174) reflects the frequency of specific digital learning activities conducted during the school year (IC174).

Nordic countries such as Denmark and Sweden show consistently high values across all indices, particularly in pedagogical intensity and access. By contrast, countries such as Germany and Greece report lower levels of digital usage and integration in teaching practices, despite similar levels of access. Bulgaria and Lithuania, while not among the highest in access, report relatively high levels of digital activities, suggesting a strong pedagogical orientation in ICT use. Notably, the mean values across countries suggest that, while access to digital infrastructure is relatively widespread (mean = 2.71 up to 4), the intensity and educational activities carried out (mean = 2.79 and 2.66 respectively, up to 5) vary more substantially and point to differentiated integration models across educational systems.

Through this comprehensive modelling approach, the analysis sheds light on which facets of ICT - both in terms of availability and actual pedagogical use - are most strongly associated with higher levels of school efficiency, while also accounting for the broader national context in which each school operates. The ICT-related variables are derived from the PISA conceptual framework, which provides internationally harmonized indicators; at the same time, their operationalization aligns closely with constructs widely recognized in the literature on educational technology and school effectiveness (Lim, 2002). In this sense, the study contributes to theory building through data, offering empirical grounding to theoretical propositions about the role of ICT in shaping school-level efficiency. By using meta-frontier techniques and multilevel analyses, the paper properly models the sources of heterogeneity and the nested structure of data.

[Tables 2 and 3] around here

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Results from the efficiency analyses

The analysis reveals a mean local efficiency score of 0.87 and a global mean of 0.69, suggesting that schools tend to perform consistently more efficiently when benchmarked against other schools within their own country rather than against the broader EU sample. This gap reflects structural, institutional, and contextual differences across education systems, which influence both the availability of resources and the constraints under which schools operate. The distribution of local and global efficiency scores is reported in Figure 1. While the right-hand shift of the local efficiency distribution is evident across countries, in some cases, such as Germany, Poland or Italy, the two distributions show a certain overlap, while in some other such as Denmark, Ireland or Sweden, the separation is even more pronounced. This latter case indicates that there are countries in which a substantial number of schools are closer to the country-specific frontier rather than to the global one. Indeed, in several cases the local scores distribution show a “peak” towards high levels of efficiency, often with a bimodal distribution. The fact that on average schools achieve higher local efficiency scores than global ones indicates that while they are performing well relative to national peers, they may lag behind the best-performing schools across Europe. These findings underscore the value of distinguishing between local and global benchmarks in efficiency analysis. While local efficiency provides a realistic assessment of performance within existing institutional and policy frameworks, global efficiency highlights potential room for improvement by identifying best practices across systems, also related with national-level educational policies. This dual perspective is essential for informing both national policy priorities and broader cross-country learning processes.

[Figure 1] around here

After running the initial efficiency model, the core of the analysis relies in assessing the influence of ICT. The conditional efficiency model includes the four ICT indexes (access_172, use_170, intensity_173, activities_174). As a result, considering ICT variables significantly affects the efficiency scores, given that the average value of the conditional efficiency is 0.85, while the global

robust unconditional score is on average equal to 0.69. The distribution of the efficiency scores by country are compared in Figure 2. A higher conditional efficiency score compared to the robust (unconditional) efficiency score indicates that, once we account for the influence of a specific contextual factor (ICT availability and use), the school gets on average closer to the frontier than in the unconditional setting. In other words, the conditional model "controls for" the external variable (e.g. level of ICT resources), allowing us to assess the school's performance relative to others with similar contextual conditions. By looking at the distributions, Denmark and Ireland appear to be among the countries mostly affected by the conditional model. Sampling schools based on their similarity in terms of ICT availability and use rather than based on a random sampling decreases inefficiencies, showing the importance of ICT in influencing the school production process. The comparison across efficiency scores is finally remarked through Table 4.

[Figure 2 and Table 4] around here

Starting from this general picture, our aim is to dig more into what aspects of ICT influence the school production function the most. Figure 3 illustrates the extent to which different dimensions of ICT are associated with the discrepancy between conditional and unconditional (robust order-m) efficiency estimates. The absolute differences presented indicate the magnitude of the contextual effect that each ICT dimension exerts on school performance, once ICT factors are accounted for. When we consider the magnitude of the difference by including each ICT index per time (left-hand barplot), the results highlight that the intensity of ICT use during PISA subject lessons (index 2) exerts the strongest influence on the conditional-unconditional efficiency gap. This suggests that integrating digital tools directly into instructional practice plays a particularly critical role in shaping school-level efficiency once contextual factors are controlled for. A similar magnitude of impact is observed for ICT use in specific educational activities (index 3) and use of specific digital resources (index 4), indicating that the manner and purpose of ICT integration matter more than sheer availability. In contrast, access and quality of digital infrastructure (index 1), while still relevant, shows a relatively smaller influence. This finding aligns with prior literature suggesting that access alone does not suffice to enhance efficiency unless accompanied by meaningful educational integration (at least in developed countries) (Tamim et al., 2011). This finding is evident also when looking at the association between ICT indexes (right-hand barplot). First, in this case the absolute difference between the conditional and unconditional model is even higher, indicating that the effect is stronger when the factors are present together. Second, the combination between indexes of ICT use is consistently more relevant than the accessibility of ICT (index 1), making more robust the claim about the relevance of ICT integration in educational activities. Overall, the results confirm that ICT use practices, rather than infrastructure per se, are the most powerful drivers of context-sensitive improvements in school efficiency. These insights underscore the need for policy interventions that move beyond hardware provision and focus on supporting teachers in embedding digital tools into instructional routines. Such an attempt is certainly related with the necessary development of digital skills for teachers (and school principals) and requires the commitment of the whole school as an organization (Cabellos et al., 2024), as well as coordinated policies at the international scale (Jackman et al., 2021).

[Figure 3] around here

4.2 Results from the multilevel random forest

To complement the rich set of results coming from the efficiency analysis, we finally aim to visualize in further detail which aspects of ICT use and access affect school efficiency more consistently. This final step of the analysis focuses on exploring the relationship between ICT-related variables (single items of the PISA questionnaire) and the previously estimated efficiency scores, with the aim of identifying which digital practices are most strongly associated with higher school-level performance. To this end, a multilevel random forest model was employed, allowing the analysis to account for the hierarchical structure of the data - namely, schools nested within countries. This approach allows to account for a much higher number of variables, providing the possibility to run the analysis at item level, as it is not possible to do directly in the efficiency estimation. In this case, the local (robust) efficiency score is the dependent variable. The ranking of importance of ICT variables is presented in Figure 4, while Figures 5 and 6 report the partial dependence plots, which show how ICT variables are related to efficiency scores.

The results are consistent with those reported in the conditional efficiency analysis, and show how the variability in efficiency scores is mainly explained by the use of ICT, in particular by the educational activities carried out in class (previously summarized by the index *actitivites_174*). Among the most impactful are those digital activities that actively engage students in cognitively demanding and autonomous tasks. For instance, schools where students more frequently elaborate their own research, work with self-collected data, and engage in independent information-seeking behavior – particularly when focused on real-world problems and phenomena – tend to display higher efficiency scores, i.e., they report higher cognitive results holding resources constant. These practices suggest a more meaningful and purposeful integration of technology into the learning process, one that goes beyond mere exposure to devices and emphasizes higher-order thinking skills. Another notable finding concerns the use of digital learning games (IC174Q10JA). When appropriately embedded in the instructional design, these tools can contribute positively to educational outcomes, as also reported by literature on effectiveness (Meggiolaro, 2018). Their association with higher efficiency highlights the potential of gamified environments to enhance the value-added component of schooling.

The partial dependence plots shown in Figure 5 provide an additional piece of information, showing the function of the association between efficiency scores and ICT items (the Figure includes the five items that appears in the top ranking of Figure 4, those who explain most of the variability in efficiency scores). This analysis also confirms a pattern observed in earlier literature: these ICT activities appear to be most effective not when used excessively, but rather when employed with moderation (Odell et al., 2020b). Partial dependence plots show that occasional (a couple of time per school year or per month), well-calibrated use of these digital tools is associated with better efficiency outcomes than intensive or continuous use. This supports the so-called "moderation hypothesis", which posits that there exists an optimal level of ICT use, beyond which the marginal benefits begin to decline or even reverse. This finding is in line with recent evidence from the literature that claim

the existence of such a relationship in effectiveness studies looking at student achievement (Meggiolaro, 2018; Odell et al., 2020b). The only exception is represented by the activity of finding information online about real-world problems/phenomena, where a greater application is connected to greater efficiency. As a final visualization tool, Figure 6 reports the partial plots of the interactions between those five variables, taken two by two. The area in yellow corresponds to the highest efficiency scores, and the plots show how the highest values emerge in correspondence of moderate use of ICT. The only exceptions are the plots involving IC174Q03JA (find information online about real-world problems), which has a positive association with efficiency, also visible in the partial plots – for example, in the interaction with IC174Q02JA (write or edit text for a school assignment). From a quantitative perspective, the multilevel random forest model explains approximately 7.82% of the total variance in school efficiency scores, a modest but meaningful proportion. Moreover, an additional 17.5% of the remaining unexplained variability is attributable to country-level differences, reflecting structural, institutional, and policy-related factors that shape the broader environment in which schools operate. Taken together, these findings provide empirical support for the idea that the impact of ICT on educational efficiency is not simply a function of access or frequency of use, but rather depends on the nature, purpose, and educational integration of digital activities within the teaching and learning process.

[Figures 4, 5, 6] around here

5. Concluding remarks

This study has examined the relationship between ICT and school efficiency across 5,360 schools in 21 European Union countries, using the latest data from the 2022 OECD PISA survey. By combining robust nonparametric efficiency models (order-m and conditional approaches) with multilevel random forest algorithms, we provide a multifaceted and methodologically novel investigation into how ICT availability and use affect school efficiency.

One of the key contributions of this study is the clear empirical support for a longstanding yet still debated proposition in the literature: that the pedagogical use of ICT contributes more significantly to educational outcomes than the availability of ICT infrastructure alone. While early research often focused on ICT inputs such as the number of devices or internet access (De Witte & Rogge, 2014), more recent studies have highlighted the critical importance of how these technologies are employed in instructional contexts (Odell et al., 2020b; Mergoni et al., 2023), and also of understanding how teachers use them and which factors shape these decisions (Dincher & Wagner, 2021) – this was particularly important during and after the COVID pandemic (Akabayashi et al., 2025). Our findings align with this perspective, showing that cognitively engaging, student-centered digital activities – such as conducting data analysis, working on real-world problems, or collaborating on digital content – are positively associated with higher efficiency scores of schools (i.e. a better use of their resources). This reinforces prior evidence that infrastructure is a necessary but not sufficient condition for effective ICT integration (Gil-Flores et al., 2017). Indeed, our conditional efficiency model shows that once ICT is accounted for, schools tend to move closer to the estimated production frontier,

especially when compared with the unconditional robust model. In other words, we find that at equal levels of resources, ICT becomes a key for supporting educational performance.

The research also has a contribution that is partially methodological. Despite the most appropriate methodological way to include contextual variables in efficiency analysis is through conditional models (as we do), we also show that adopting machine learning techniques to better visualize the interactions between variables produce consistent results and innovative insights. Future research could advance even more this kind of integration.

Finally, our findings suggest that not only what ICT is used but also how often it is used matters. Echoing Meggiolaro (2018) and Odell et al. (2020b), we confirm the existence of a “moderation hypothesis”: moderate use of digital tools – rather than continuous or overly intensive application – tends to be associated with the highest efficiency outcomes. This has strong implications for educational policy and practice. Schools should be encouraged not merely to increase digital exposure but to design instructional uses of ICT that are purposeful, pedagogically aligned, and mindful of cognitive load and screen fatigue. In this line, the indications and prescriptions outlined by the EU Commission’s DigCompEdu (European Commission, 2017) appear as necessary guidelines to be implemented with more political and managerial commitment, going beyond the risk of simplistic policies like banning smartphones from schools, that appear somehow ineffective (Kessel et al., 2020). Recent experiments – in the different context of primary schools, in a developing country – suggest that integrating digital platforms in regular classes with a clear pedagogical design can have large positive effects on academic results (Araya et al., 2025).

In sum, this study advances the empirical basis for a more nuanced and theory-informed understanding of ICT's role in school efficiency. It contributes to ongoing debate about the role of ICT in the educational process, by providing empirical evidence that can be translated into actionable insights. For policy makers, evidence suggests that investments in ICT infrastructure and digital tools should be complemented by efforts to build teacher capacity in digital pedagogy. Professional development programs should prioritize not just the technical skills required to operate digital tools, but also instructional strategies that promote deep learning and cognitive engagement. For school leaders, the findings highlight the importance of creating a school-wide culture that supports purposeful and balanced use of digital technologies. Monitoring how ICT is used – together with how often – is crucial. Principals should encourage applications that support student critical thinking, and facilitate peer exchange around effective digital teaching, together with spreading the culture towards a moderate and purposeful use of ICT. To this end, we can conclude and confirm that a real “human touch” is necessary for a clever use of technology in education; this is even truer in the recent context of widespread use of GenAI by students and teachers. Indeed, even advanced adaptive learning facilitated by the use of dedicated software can guarantee better academic results, as demonstrated by Van Klaveren (2017).

While this study provides a comprehensive, cross-national analysis using state-of-the-art methodologies, limitations must be acknowledged. First, the analysis relies on cross-sectional data, which limits causal inference. Longitudinal designs would help identify whether ICT use predicts performance gains over time. Second, the ICT indices are constructed from self-reported survey items, which may introduce reporting biases or lack objective precision. Future work could combine

survey data with classroom observations or learning analytics to triangulate findings. In conclusion, this study underscores the importance of moving beyond simple measures of ICT availability toward more nuanced understandings of how technology is integrated into teaching and learning. By doing so, it contributes providing actionable evidence for improving digital education policy and practice. Future research should continue to explore the mechanisms through which ICT affects school production, possibly integrating measures of non-cognitive skills and examining longitudinal effects over time.

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Table 1. Descriptive statistics of inputs and outputs per country – number of observations, mean and standard deviations

CNT	N (schools)	ESCS mean (sd)	EDURICH mean (sd)	TSRATIO mean (sd)	MATH SCORE mean (sd)	READING SCORE mean (sd)	SCIENCE SCORE mean (sd)
AUT	258	-0.015 (0.597)	3.972 (1.080)	0.111 (0.034)	479.517 (69.335)	472.045 (77.655)	481.503 (74.669)
BEL	217	0.098 (0.527)	3.778 (0.876)	0.130 (0.071)	495.046 (71.640)	481.852 (73.873)	493.526 (72.944)
BGR	166	-0.363 (0.765)	4.080 (0.886)	0.096 (0.028)	410.748 (70.947)	396.973 (78.213)	414.842 (69.297)
CZE	414	-0.130 (0.574)	3.661 (0.842)	0.086 (0.030)	484.630 (69.588)	484.745 (72.426)	494.819 (73.898)
DEU	180	-0.195 (0.588)	3.605 (0.977)	0.077 (0.027)	472.492 (65.981)	476.306 (72.143)	489.178 (73.423)
DNK	268	0.332 (0.399)	4.229 (0.771)	0.090 (0.048)	477.982 (37.350)	477.470 (43.894)	479.936 (44.080)
ESP	810	-0.022 (0.474)	3.789 (1.032)	0.102 (0.048)	477.116 (39.764)	476.881 (43.578)	489.638 (37.993)
EST	192	0.087 (0.431)	3.701 (0.909)	0.100 (0.040)	507.857 (40.019)	508.974 (40.218)	523.084 (39.898)
FIN	222	0.199 (0.311)	4.082 (0.845)	0.099 (0.045)	477.476 (32.772)	481.109 (38.930)	501.257 (40.195)
GRC	219	-0.205 (0.500)	2.899 (1.176)	0.133 (0.073)	427.442 (49.302)	431.852 (58.318)	436.643 (54.938)
HRV	164	-0.155 (0.429)	3.290 (0.965)	0.120 (0.048)	462.093 (56.707)	474.590 (58.116)	482.435 (55.965)
HUN	209	-0.148 (0.723)	3.210 (1.064)	0.101 (0.047)	452.763 (80.846)	452.718 (85.578)	467.592 (78.732)
IRL	150	0.315 (0.372)	4.161 (0.846)	0.086 (0.035)	491.308 (30.870)	516.265 (32.987)	503.205 (34.295)
ITA	309	-0.176 (0.553)	3.856 (0.945)	0.162 (0.102)	466.035 (63.890)	470.769 (61.297)	472.056 (65.518)
LTU	275	-0.151 (0.600)	3.810 (0.747)	0.110 (0.061)	455.794 (54.832)	449.530 (61.200)	462.739 (59.228)
LVA	187	-0.132 (0.476)	3.225 (0.841)	0.112 (0.047)	474.811 (40.852)	466.743 (45.719)	484.947 (41.418)
POL	234	-0.153 (0.544)	3.916 (0.916)	0.118 (0.070)	483.232 (65.027)	483.035 (72.277)	493.871 (65.856)
ROU	256	-0.541 (0.726)	3.286 (1.116)	0.077 (0.055)	411.543 (75.136)	409.722 (77.562)	414.424 (73.361)
SVK	259	-0.408 (0.610)	3.375 (1.102)	0.091 (0.034)	454.856 (69.151)	437.845 (69.211)	452.052 (71.338)
SVN	309	-0.001 (0.552)	3.794 (0.871)	0.177 (0.156)	456.649 (63.403)	441.634 (69.098)	470.673 (68.957)
SWE	204	0.341 (0.396)	4.167 (0.829)	0.090 (0.040)	487.546 (52.846)	492.839 (61.443)	499.317 (57.171)

Note: AUT=Austria; BEL=Belgium; BGR=Bulgaria; CZE=Czech Republic; DEU=Germany; DNK=Denmark; ESP=Spain; EST=Estonia; FIN=Finland; GRC=Greece; HRV=Croatia; HUN=Hungary; IRL=Ireland; ITA=Italy; LTU=Lithuania; LVA=Latvia; POL=Poland; ROU=Romania; SVK=Slovakia; SVN=Slovenia; SWE=Sweden. ESCS: socio-economic status; EDURICH: index of 'richness' of educational resources; TSRATIO: teacher-student ratio.

Table 2. List of items of ICT availability and use and aggregation into ICT indexes

Index	Variable Code	Question Description	Scale
access_172	IC172Q01JA	There are enough digital resources for every student at my school.	Agreement - 1 to 4
	IC172Q02JA	There are enough digital devices with access to the Internet at my school.	Agreement - 1 to 4
	IC172Q03JA	The school's Internet speed is sufficient.	Agreement - 1 to 4
	IC172Q04JA	Digital resources function properly at my school.	Agreement - 1 to 4
	IC172Q05JA	Digital resources are easily accessible within the classroom.	Agreement - 1 to 4
	IC172Q06JA	Digital learning resources make learning interesting.	Agreement - 1 to 4
	IC172Q07JA	The school provides sufficient technical support.	Agreement - 1 to 4
	IC172Q08JA	Teachers have the necessary skills to use digital devices.	Agreement - 1 to 4
	IC172Q09JA	Teachers are willing to use digital resources for teaching.	Agreement - 1 to 4
use_170	IC170Q01JA	Use desktop or laptop computer.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC170Q02JA	Use smartphone with Internet access.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC170Q03JA	Use tablet device or e-book reader.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC170Q04JA	Use Internet access (non-smartphone).	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC170Q05JA	Use school portal.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC170Q06JA	Use educational software, games, or apps.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC170Q07JA	Use learning management system/platform.	Frequency - 1 to 5
intensity_173	IC173Q01JA	Digital resource use in <test language> lessons.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC173Q02JA	Digital resource use in mathematics lessons.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC173Q03JA	Digital resource use in science lessons.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC173Q04JA	Digital resource use in computer science/IT lessons.	Frequency - 1 to 5
activities_174	IC174Q01JA	Create a multimedia presentation.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC174Q02JA	Write or edit text for a school assignment.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC174Q03JA	Find information online about real-world problems.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC174Q04JA	Collect and record data.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC174Q05JA	Analyze data collected.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC174Q06JA	Report or share results from experiments.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC174Q07JA	Plan and manage work or projects.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC174Q08JA	Track the progress of work or projects.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC174Q09JA	Collaborate to create digital content.	Frequency - 1 to 5
	IC174Q10JA	Play digital learning games.	Frequency - 1 to 5

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the 4 indexes of ICT availability and use employed in the analysis

Country	access_172	use_170	intensity_173	activities_174
AUT	2.723	3.469	2.735	2.598
BEL	2.676	3.431	2.665	2.609
BGR	2.644	3.392	2.975	3.012
CZE	2.662	3.431	2.525	2.404
DEU	2.436	2.850	2.538	2.333
DNK	2.874	4.183	4.212	3.321
ESP	2.686	2.912	2.732	2.773
EST	2.810	3.031	2.439	2.487
FIN	2.865	3.720	2.756	2.670
GRC	2.528	2.890	2.579	2.426
HRV	2.768	3.375	2.623	2.643
HUN	2.704	3.439	2.715	2.685
IRL	2.768	2.962	2.798	2.632
ITA	2.649	3.307	2.811	2.728
LTU	2.750	3.361	2.867	2.828
LVA	2.722	3.432	2.588	2.575
POL	2.508	3.487	2.717	2.531
ROU	2.788	3.056	2.724	2.669
SVK	2.620	3.090	2.652	2.536
SVN	2.771	3.413	2.451	2.467
SWE	2.962	3.922	3.488	3.001
Mean	2.710	3.341	2.790	2.663

Note: AUT=Austria; BEL=Belgium; BGR=Bulgaria; CZE=Czech Republic; DEU=Germany; DNK=Denmark; ESP=Spain; EST=Estonia; FIN=Finland; GRC=Greece; HRV=Croatia; HUN=Hungary; IRL=Ireland; ITA=Italy; LTU=Lithuania; LVA=Latvia; POL=Poland; ROU=Romania; SVK=Slovakia; SVN=Slovenia; SWE=Sweden. Access_172: index of digital availability and quality, based on items from question set IC172; use_170: how frequently schools use different types of digital devices and platforms, as reported in IC170; intensity_173: how often digital tools are used in various subject lessons (IC173); activities_174: frequency of specific digital learning activities conducted during the school year (IC174).

Figure 1. Distribution of local and global efficiency scores by country

Note: AUT=Austria; BEL=Belgium; BGR=Bulgaria; CZE=Czech Republic; DEU=Germany; DNK=Denmark; ESP=Spain; EST=Estonia; FIN=Finland; GRC=Greece; HRV=Croatia; HUN=Hungary; IRL=Ireland; ITA=Italy; LTU=Lithuania; LVA=Latvia; POL=Poland; ROU=Romania; SVK=Slovakia; SVN=Slovenia; SWE=Sweden.

Figure 2. Distribution of global and conditional efficiency scores by country

Note: AUT=Austria; BEL=Belgium; BGR=Bulgaria; CZE=Czech Republic; DEU=Germany; DNK=Denmark; ESP=Spain; EST=Estonia; FIN=Finland; GRC=Greece; HRV=Croatia; HUN=Hungary; IRL=Ireland; ITA=Italy; LTU=Lithuania; LVA=Latvia; POL=Poland; ROU=Romania; SVK=Slovakia; SVN=Slovenia; SWE=Sweden.

Table 4. Mean and standard deviation of the local, global and conditional efficiency scores by country

Country	Local efficiency (robust)		Global efficiency (robust)		Conditional efficiency	
	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd
AUT	0.870	0.102	0.688	0.095	0.841	0.102
BEL	0.903	0.084	0.692	0.086	0.822	0.090
BGR	0.894	0.115	0.616	0.107	0.811	0.119
CZE	0.881	0.085	0.717	0.087	0.900	0.076
DEU	0.872	0.091	0.728	0.098	0.915	0.083
DNK	0.893	0.074	0.665	0.049	0.899	0.083
ESP	0.846	0.086	0.693	0.069	0.858	0.091
EST	0.923	0.072	0.731	0.053	0.862	0.069
FIN	0.914	0.072	0.690	0.048	0.809	0.078
GRC	0.836	0.118	0.653	0.109	0.800	0.110
HRV	0.916	0.080	0.686	0.081	0.829	0.084
HUN	0.874	0.115	0.697	0.106	0.872	0.099
IRL	0.944	0.053	0.712	0.036	0.833	0.070
ITA	0.719	0.127	0.661	0.091	0.812	0.088
LTU	0.888	0.097	0.655	0.078	0.836	0.100
LVA	0.876	0.114	0.697	0.078	0.842	0.084
POL	0.878	0.094	0.699	0.095	0.871	0.085
ROU	0.828	0.110	0.708	0.140	0.910	0.097
SVK	0.865	0.102	0.709	0.112	0.898	0.089
SVN	0.834	0.115	0.647	0.092	0.776	0.108
SWE	0.928	0.069	0.680	0.054	0.867	0.089

Note: AUT=Austria; BEL=Belgium; BGR=Bulgaria; CZE=Czech Republic; DEU=Germany; DNK=Denmark; ESP=Spain; EST=Estonia; FIN=Finland; GRC=Greece; HRV=Croatia; HUN=Hungary; IRL=Ireland; ITA=Italy; LTU=Lithuania; LVA=Latvia; POL=Poland; ROU=Romania; SVK=Slovakia; SVN=Slovenia; SWE=Sweden.

Figure 3. Barplots reporting the magnitude of the effect of the ICT indexes on the school production function, but individually and by pairs of indexes

Note: On the y axis, the magnitude of the effects is reported (see Eq. (7)). On the x axis, the left-hand graph reports the singular ICT index considered in the conditional analysis; the right-hand graph reports the ICT indexes considered in the conditional analysis two by two. 1= access_172; 2= intensity_173; 3= activities_174; 4= use_170.

Figure 4. ICT variables importance plot

Note. The plot shows the relative importance of each variable regarding ICT in the Random Forest model, based on the Increase in Node Purity (represented on the horizontal axis). This measure indicates how much each variable contributes to reducing the model’s overall impurity, meaning variables with higher values are more influential in making accurate predictions. However, it is important to note that this metric reflects importance but not the direction of the relationship (i.e., whether the variable increases or decreases the predicted outcome). The variable “random” is indeed a random normally distributed variable introduced to check what variables are more important than a random one.

Figure 5. Partial dependence plot of the five most relevant ICT variables

Note: IC174Q10JA=Play digital learning games; IC174Q06JA=Report or share results from experiments; IC174Q05JA=Analyse data collected; IC174Q03JA=Find information online about real-world problems; IC174Q02JA=Write or edit text for a school assignment. X-axis reports frequency of use: 1=Never or almost never; 2=About once or twice a year; 3=About once or twice a month; 4=About once or twice a week; 5=Every day or almost every day. Y-axis reports the interval of variation of the efficiency score. Thus, each partial dependence plot illustrates how the predicted outcome changes as a single ICT variable varies, while keeping all other variables constant (on average). It helps interpret the direction and shape of the relationship between that variable and the model's prediction.

Figure 6. Partial dependence plot of the interaction among the five most relevant ICT variables

Note: The figure shows two-way partial dependence plots illustrating how pairs of variables jointly influence the model's predictions. Predicted values reported in legend refer to variation in school efficiency. In the color scale, yellow areas indicate higher predicted school efficiency, while blue areas correspond to lower predicted efficiency, allowing a visual interpretation of how different combinations of the two variables are associated with better or worse outcomes. IC174Q10JA=Play digital learning games; IC174Q06JA=Report or share results from experiments; IC174Q05JA=Analyse data collected; IC174Q03JA=Find information online about real-world problems; IC174Q02JA=Write or edit text for a school assignment.